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Tomodensitometric aspects of Metastatic Breast Cancer seen in medical
imaging in University Hospital Center Luxembourg

Camara MA¹, Coulibaly S², Mariko M⁴, Traore MM¹, Ndiaye M⁴, Kone AS¹, Kane AST⁴,
Diarra H¹, Tangare M⁶, Coulibaly S¹, Toure Sbm¹ and Sidibe S⁶

¹Imagerie Médicale Department Of Hôpital du Mali, West Africa

²Imagerie Médicale Department Of CHU de Kati, West Africa

³Imagerie Médicale department Of Centre H le Luxembourg, West Africa

⁴Hopital Infirmérie de Bamako, West Africa

⁵Department of Radiothérapie of Hôpital du Mali, West Africa

⁶Imagerie Médicale department of CHU POINT G, West Africa

*Corresponding Author: Dr CAMARA Mody Abdoulaye, Radiologist /Hôpital du Mali, Bamako, Mali, West Africa, Tel: +223 66 72 25 80

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Abstract

Introduction: Breast cancer is the first cancer in woman worldwide. Its prognosis depends on early diagnosis and treatment. CT-scan has an important place in the diagnostic screening and the surveillance of this disease. The goal of this study was to assess the place of CT-scan in extension screening of breast cancer in the Department of Medical Imaging of the Teaching Hospital Mother-Child "Le Luxembourg".

Methods: It is a descriptive study on the retrospective compilation of CT-scan data of patients in the Department of Medical Imaging of the Teaching Hospital Mother-Child "Le Luxembourg" from May 1st to November 30th 2017. Were enrolled all patients, regardless of gender or age, with breast cancer histologically confirmed and who developed at least one secondary lesion found by CT-scan. CT-scan was performed before and after treatment. CT-scan machines were HITACHI® SUPRIA 16 bars and TOSHIBA® 04 bars, without and with Iodine 350mg intravenous injection.

Results: Over seven months, 44 patients were enrolled with a mean age of 49 years and females were predominant. A family history of breast cancer was found in 13% of cases and invasive ductal carcinoma represented 95.54%. The main metastases were multi visceral (31.82%), pleural pulmonary (70.75%), ganglionic (63.63%), hepatic (27.27%) and bone (18.18%).

Conclusion: Breast cancer is a public health concern with a clear predominance of women. In our context, CT-scan still has an important place in the research of secondary lesion in addition to the surveillance of this disease.

Keywords: CT-scan Breast cancer; Metastasis; UHC Luxembourg

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